

DETECTION OF A SMALL SIZE DAMAGE IN A UNIFORM BEAM AND PIPE USING VIBRATORY POWER FROM THE MEASURED VELOCITIES BY A LASER SCANNING VIBROMETER

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ABSTRACT

Vibratory power is defined as the rate of energy transmitted in a vibrating structure. The spatial distribution of vibratory power provides useful information about structural health. If a structure is damaged, the path of energy will be altered near the damage. Vibratory power can be estimated experimentally by measuring accelerations and the damage location can be identified from the changes of vibratory power.

In general, high frequency excitations are required to detect small size damages. The vibratory power needs to be estimated in high frequency range in order to identify the small size damage. It is necessary to measure the accelerations at dense interval due to the short wavelength at high frequency. However, measuring acceleration response of a structure at dense interval using conventional accelerometers is a formidable task for certain structures. Being a non-contact sensor, a laser scanning vibrometer can measure the structural response without spatial limitation.

In this study, we have estimated vibration power in a uniform beam by a laser scanning vibrometer. An exciter is installed beneath the center of the beam and generates random signals in the frequency range of 2-20 kHz. An artificial damage is inflicted by saw on the top surface of the beam. The damage has a depth of 1mm that corresponds to the ratio of 0.1 over the beam height. Vibratory power is estimated from the measured velocities in up to a frequency range of 20 kHz. The damage index can be calculated from the changes in vibratory power between the undamaged and damaged beam. The damage index has maximum value near the damage. As a result, a small size damage can be identified successfully using vibratory power estimated from the velocity data obtained by a laser scanning vibrometer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Vibratory power is defined as the rate of energy transmitted through a cross section of unit width in a vibrating structure. The spatial distribution of the vibratory power provides information about the propagation of energy through the structure. If there are damages in the structural members, the path of energy will be altered near the damages. The basic formulae describing vibratory power in the far field were proposed first by Noiseux [1]. Pavic [2] extended these formulae to the near field problem using the finite difference method. Verheij [3] and Linjama [4] proposed a practical procedure to estimate vibratory power based on a cross-spectral density method and a frequency response method, respectively. Gavric et al. [5] showed that the input power at a source point is the same as vibratory power passing through a closed curve including the source point.

While there exist several analytical studies to estimate the vibratory power of damaged structures, only a few attempts have been made to identify the damage for practical implementations. Based on the transfer matrix method [6, 7] or the spectral finite element method [8], vibratory power of one-dimensional beam with an open crack was analysed. Lee et al. [9] calculated the forced response of a rectangular plate with surface cracks using the commercial finite element analysis code, and investigated the characteristics of vibratory power in the vicinity of a crack. Wong et al. [10] proposed damage identification techniques based on modal reactive power. However, experimental validation was not included in these previous numerical studies. Recently, a new approach based on vibratory power has been proposed to identify the damage in a prismatic beam and a rectangular plate [11, 12]. The numerical simulations and experimental studies are carried out to validate the proposed method. The damage and its location can be successfully identified by the proposed method.

It is well known that excitation frequency should be high to identify a small size damage [13]. Vibratory power needs to be estimated in a high frequency range to detect the small size damage. Therefore, it is necessary to measure the accelerations at dense intervals between two adjacent accelerometers since the wavelength of a vibrating structure is very short at high frequencies. However, there are some difficulties in measuring accelerations of a structure at dense intervals using conventional accelerometers, which are directly attached to a structure, due to their structural shapes. While a laser scanning vibrometer, being a non-contact sensor, can measure the structural responses without spatial limitation. In this paper, we have estimated vibration power in a uniform beam by a laser scanning vibrometer. Spring-damped conditions by sand are applied to both ends of the beam to reduce the reflected waves from the boundaries. The beam is randomly excited by an electric exciter in the frequency range of 2- 20 kHz. Artificial damage is inflicted by saw on the top surface of the beam. The vibratory power is estimated by measuring velocity data up to a frequency range of 20 kHz. The damage index can be calculated from the changes in vibratory power between the undamaged and damaged beam. The damage index near the damage is obtained as a result, which enable us to identify the damage location without ambiguity. Consequently a small size damage is identified successfully using vibratory power estimated from the velocity data by a laser scanning vibrometer.

2 DAMAGE IDENTIFICATION IN BEAMS USING VIBRATORY POWER

2.1 Vibratory power

In a vibrating beam, the inner product of internal forces, which are shear force and bending moment, with the corresponding generalized velocities yields the power transmitting through a cross section of unit width [1]. Based on Euler-Bernoulli beam theory, the shear force and bending moment are proportional to spatial derivatives of vertical displacement w . The spatial derivatives of the vertical displacement w can be approximated by the finite difference of w with a line array of four sensors as shown in Figure 1. For a uniform beam with its axis oriented along the x coordinate, the time-averaged vibratory power can be expressed as follows [2]:

$$\langle P(x;t) \rangle_T = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T EI \left(\frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial t} \right) dt = \frac{EI}{\Delta^3} \langle 4\dot{w}_2 w_3 - \dot{w}_2 w_4 - \dot{w}_1 w_3 \rangle_T, \quad (1)$$

where $I = bh^3/12$, and b and h are the width and the height of the beam. Δ is the distance between two adjacent sensors. E is the Young's modulus and w_i is the vertical displacement measured at point i .

Figure 1: Line array with four sensors.

The time-averaged vibratory power can be expressed in a spectral form by the Fourier transform. In practice, the vibratory power spectrum is obtained from the frequency response functions of the velocities measured in the line array as follows [4].

$$P(x; \omega) \cong \frac{EI}{\omega \Delta^3} \text{Im} \left\{ (4H_{F2}^* H_{F3} - H_{F2}^* H_{F4} - H_{F1}^* H_{F3}) G_{FF} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\text{Im}\{\cdot\}$ is imaginary part of $\{\cdot\}$ and the asterisk denotes the complex conjugate. $H_{Fi}(\omega)$ is the frequency response function between the force signal and velocity at the i th position, and $G_{FF}(\omega)$ is the auto-spectrum of the forcing signal.

2.2 Damage index

If the internal damping is ignored and the external force is constant, the vibratory power in Eq. (2) should be the same over the entire beam regardless of the damage. The flexural rigidity decreases at the point where the damage is generated, while the vibratory power normalized by assigning a unit value to the flexural rigidity should increase at the damage location. For the sake of the experimental convenience, we can normalize Eq. (2) by assigning a unit value to the flexural rigidity and propose the damage index that is independent of the flexural rigidity. In the previous study [11, 12], the damage index was demonstrated to be a useful quantity for identifying the damage location and its severity. The damage index at any point x_k can be expressed as follows.

$$DI_{x_k} = \frac{\left| \int_{\omega_{lw}}^{\omega_{up}} \tilde{P}_2(x_k; \omega) d\omega - \int_{\omega_{lw}}^{\omega_{up}} \tilde{P}_1(x_k; \omega) d\omega \right|}{\max \left[\int_{\omega_{lw}}^{\omega_{up}} \tilde{P}_1(x_i; \omega) d\omega \right]}, \quad (i = 1, \dots, k, \dots, n) \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{P}_1(x; \omega)$, $\tilde{P}_2(x; \omega)$ are the vibratory powers in the intact state and the current state, respectively. The tilde of P implies the vibratory power is normalized by assigning a unit value to the flexural rigidity. ω_1 and ω_2 are the upper and lower bounds of the frequency integral by considering the wavelength over the sensor spacing, λ/Δ .

3 EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

3.1 Experiment set up

A uniform beam is made of pure aluminium. The length, width and height of the beam are 2.0 m, 0.03 m and 0.01 m, respectively. The elastic modulus and density are 70 GPa and 2710 kg/m³. At both ends of the beam, wooden boxes filled with sand are installed, and the ends of the beam are buried in the sand in order to reduce the reflective waves from the boundary. Artificial damage is inflicted by making a fine saw cut on the top surface of the beam at -0.35 m apart from the centre. The damage has depth of 1 mm, which corresponds to the 10% of the beam height. The specimen is shown in Figure 2.

The measurement system consists of a laser scanning vibrometer (PSV-400) and the vibrometer controller with junction box (PSV-A-010). The electric exciter (B&K Type 4809), with a useful frequency range of 2-20 kHz, is installed under the beam. The exciter is driven by signals from an internal function generator of PSV-A-010. The signal from PSV-A-010 passes through the power amplifier (B&K Type 2706). The impedance head (B&K Type 8001) is fixed between the exciter and beam. The force signals measured from the impedance head are transmitted to PSV-A-010 and used as reference signals for measuring the frequency response functions (FRFs). The beam is subjected to random excitation with frequencies ranging from 2 Hz to 20 kHz considering the maximum frequency of the exciter. The velocity responses of the beam are measured around the damage by PSV-400. As for data acquisition, the sampling frequency is set to 128 kHz, the frequency resolution to 4 Hz, and the ensemble average to 200 times. An overview of the measurement system is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Inflicted damage by saw cut ($a/h = 0.1$).

Figure 3: Overview of the measurement system.

3.2 Power estimation and damage index

Before the estimation of the vibratory power in structures, it is necessary to determine the sensor spacing. Since the vibratory power is estimated on the basis of the finite difference approximation, the accuracy is dependent on the adequate sensor spacing, Δ . Numerical error caused by finite difference approximation increases at high frequency. While, at low frequency, bias error due to phase mismatch between two accelerometers can occur or low coherence causes random errors [14, 15]. Therefore, the frequency bandwidth for the spectral analysis should be chosen to maintain the wavelength, λ from 7 to 14 times longer than sensor spacing, Δ [11]. Physically, λ/Δ implies the number of sensors that can be placed in one wavelength.

By means of PSV-400, the velocity responses of the beam are measured in the 100 mm length near the damage. The vibratory powers for the undamaged and damaged beam are estimated from the frequency response functions of measured velocities. For the convenience of the experimental study, the sensor spacing is chosen as 5.0 mm, 7.5 mm and 10 mm. In the case of 5.0 mm, the allowable range of frequency is from 18.81 kHz to 75.25 kHz. In the case of 7.5 mm, the allowable range is from 8.36 kHz to 33.45 kHz. The allowable range is from 4.7 kHz to 18.81 kHz in the case of 10 mm. However, the upper limit of frequency integral should be 20 kHz because of the maximum frequency of exciter. Consequently, the allowable range of frequency for each value of Δ is determined as shown in Table 1. Figure 4 compares the vibratory powers of undamaged and damaged beam. We can see that the vibratory power of damaged beam is higher than that of undamaged beam near the damage (at $x = -0.35$ m). In the case of 5.0 mm, the vibratory power of undamaged and damaged beam is not clearly

separated near the damage. This is because the excitation frequency is not high enough for this particular spacing.

Table 1 Allowable range of frequency bandwidth and the corresponding λ/Δ

Sensor spacing, Δ	Allowable range of frequency, f	Corresponding range of λ/Δ
5.0 mm	$18.8 \text{ kHz} \leq f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$	$13.6 \leq \lambda/\Delta \leq 14.0$
7.5 mm	$8.4 \text{ kHz} \leq f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$	$9.1 \leq \lambda/\Delta \leq 14.0$
10 mm	$4.7 \text{ kHz} \leq f \leq 18.8 \text{ kHz}$	$7.0 \leq \lambda/\Delta \leq 14.0$

Figure 4: Comparison of the vibratory power between the undamaged and damaged beam

The damage index indicates the change in the vibratory power of the current state relative to that of the intact state. The damage index of the beam is calculated by Eq. (3) and the result is shown in Figure 5. We can observe that the values of the index are high in the vicinity of the damage compared with the other regions of the beam. However, in the case of 5.0 mm, the damage index near the damage is not very pronounced compared with other locations. Hence we cannot identify the damage location clearly. In the case of 10 mm, the damage location is identified clearly by the damage index, while the maximum value of the index is about 0.08 that is a low level. The most favorable result is obtained from the case of 7.5 mm. It shows that the proposed method can identify and localize the small size damage of the uniform beam. However to get useful information the ratio λ/Δ should be within appropriate range.

Figure 5: Damage index of the beam having a small size damage

4 CONCLUSIONS

The time average of vibratory power is obtained from vertical velocity data measured on the uniform beam by a laser scanning vibrometer. A damage index is proposed based on the change in the vibratory power of the current state and applied to the identification of a small size damage. In order to identify a small size damage, the vibratory power needs to be estimated in a high frequency range. Since a laser scanning vibrometer, being a non-contact sensor, can measure the structural responses at dense intervals, the vibratory power and damage index could be obtained in high frequency range using a laser scanning vibrometer. For the convenience of the experimental study, the sensor spacing is chosen as 5.0 mm, 7.5 mm and 10 mm.

The vibratory power of damaged beam is higher than that of undamaged beam near the damage (at $x = -0.35$ m). Furthermore, the values of the index are high in the vicinity of the damage compared with the other undamaged part of the beam. However, in the case of 5.0 mm, the damage index near the damage is not so pronounced compared with that of undamaged region. To get useful information the ratio λ/Δ should be within appropriate range. Under the laboratory environment, it is shown that the proposed method can identify and localize a small size damage of a uniform beam.

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